

Understanding the Performance Plateau in Text-to-Video Retrieval: A Comprehensive Empirical and Linguistic Analysis

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Abstract

Text-to-video retrieval enables users to find relevant video content using natural language queries, a task that has grown increasingly important with the rapid expansion of online video. Over the past six years (2020–2025), research has produced numerous methods, such as dual encoders, attention-driven models, and multimodal fusion approaches; however, fundamental questions remain about model behavior, dataset influence, and query difficulty. In this work, we evaluate 14 state-of-the-art retrieval methods across 3 widely used datasets under a unified preprocessing and evaluation framework. We analyze caption characteristics, including length, clarity, semantic category, and Action vs. Scene balance, and link these to model performance. Our results show that short, clear, and simple captions, such as those describing single actions or color attributes, achieve higher recall, while complex events, multi-step activities, or fine-grained scene descriptions remain challenging for all existing models. Attention-driven architectures better handle temporally dependent or multi-step queries, whereas dual-encoder and multimodal fusion models perform well primarily on simpler or single-category captions. Cross-dataset generalization improves with larger, more diverse caption sets, but generative captions do not consistently enhance retrieval accuracy. Overall, our findings highlight key dataset factors, benchmark challenges, and the interplay between query content and model architecture, providing guidance for developing more effective text-to-video retrieval systems.

Keywords: Text-to-Video Retrieval, Video Search, Query-log Analysis

Fig. 1: Recall@10 (left y -axis) and model complexity in FLOPs (right y -axis, black line) from 2021 to 2025 for various methods and datasets. Methods are sorted chronologically by year and alphabetically within the same year (x -axis). Datasets are shown as LSMDC (orange), MSRVTT (blue), MSVD (green). Year blocks are highlighted with soft background colors: 2021 (light gray), 2022 (blue), 2023 (yellow), 2024 (soft green), 2025 (red/pink).

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of online video content has made effective video retrieval a fundamental challenge for multimedia systems. Users increasingly rely on natural language queries to search, browse, and explore large video collections, motivating extensive research on text-to-video retrieval. This task enables applications such as semantic video search, digital assistants, recommendation systems, and interactive multimedia exploration. Over the past six years, advances in large-scale datasets and pretrained vision-language models have driven substantial progress in retrieval performance [1–6, 6–27]. As multimedia content continues to grow in scale and complexity, navigation and search become increasingly challenging. Text-based search [7, 28–49] has emerged as the most natural interface for users on text-to-video retrieval and it can be viewed as a direct extension of the way people already search the web. Over the past six years, the research focus shows that the majority of research concentrates on text-to-video retrieval, supporting applications such as semantic search [50], digital assistants [51], and video recommendation [52]. This strong focus has been reinforced by improvements in datasets [53] and the availability of powerful pretrained models. Recent progress has been driven by a variety of architectures [54–56], such as dual encoders [14, 36, 44, 57], multimodal fusion approaches [7, 58, 59], transformer based architectures [60–62], and attention driven systems [63–65].

A further challenge in the field is the lack of consistent and principled evaluation practices. Many recent methods are compared primarily against a small set of baselines, often CLIP4CLIP, while direct comparisons among newer approaches are limited. Evaluation protocols, preprocessing choices, and reporting standards vary across studies, making it difficult to draw reliable conclusions about relative performance. Moreover, most works focus exclusively on aggregate metrics such as Recall@k, offering little insight into why certain methods succeed or fail. Figure 1 presents the Recall@10 performance from 2020 to 2025. Specifically, it shows a rapid initial improvement, followed by a slow plateau, even as model complexity—measured in

floating-point operations—has continued to increase. In several cases, highly complex models achieve performance comparable to lighter, more efficient approaches, suggesting diminishing returns from architectural scaling alone. Model complexity (in FLOPs) increased up to 2022 but later shifted toward lighter, parameter-efficient models (e.g., DGL [32]). In addition, higher complexity does not always translate into higher performance. For example, X-CLIP [66] and XPOOL [39] are highly complex yet achieve recall similar to medium-complexity models, while TempMe [67] achieves competitive performance with lower complexity.

Moreover, performance also varies significantly across datasets, and the field lacks principled explanations for why certain methods succeed or fail. Some queries are consistently easy for all models, while others remain challenging regardless of the architecture. Most studies report only aggregate metrics, rarely analyzing temporal trends, dataset-specific differences, or qualitative behavior. Few examine the nature of positive and negative matches or identify challenging query types [68]. Despite diverse architectures (discussed in detail in Section 2), a comprehensive understanding of linguistic properties, semantic categories, and dataset composition, and other factors driving performance differences across systems and datasets is still lacking.

To address these gaps, we present a comprehensive analysis of text-to-video retrieval that focuses on query characteristics, dataset properties, and model behavior rather than proposing a new architecture. We evaluate 14 representative state-of-the-art retrieval methods across three widely used benchmark datasets under a unified preprocessing and evaluation framework. A central focus is the role of dataset annotations: datasets with multiple captions per video capture richer semantic variability and reveal strengths and weaknesses that single-caption datasets fail to expose. We identify which retrieval tasks are consistently easy or difficult, how model behaviors align or diverge, and which semantic categories pose challenges across all systems. Our findings indicate that simple descriptions, such as single actions or color attributes, are generally handled reliably, while tasks involving complex events, multi-step activities, or fine-grained scene understanding remain challenging for all existing models.

In addition to standard metrics [69], we analyze the linguistic structure of captions using semantic similarity embeddings [70, 71], syntactic complexity measures [72, 73], and category-based clustering. This approach allows us to quantify how textual properties influence retrieval behavior and whether certain models respond consistently to specific linguistic patterns. The resulting clusters show that performance differences arise not only from architectural choices, but also from how models interpret and prioritize different forms of linguistic information. Attention-driven models such as TempMe and UATVR [74] are better suited to temporally dependent or multi-step queries, while dual-encoder and multimodal fusion approaches perform well primarily on simpler or single-category descriptions. We further show that datasets with multiple captions per video provide more informative and challenging evaluation settings, leading to improved cross-dataset generalization, whereas single-caption datasets can overestimate performance.

Finally, we investigate the influence of caption quantity and quality across datasets. We show that datasets with many captions per video provide more informative and challenging evaluation settings, while single caption datasets can artificially inflate

performance by reducing semantic diversity. We also test the use of generative captions, finding that automatically generated descriptions do not consistently improve retrieval accuracy and often introduce noise. These results show that the number and quality of captions are key for benchmarking and should guide dataset design.

The main contributions of this survey are presented as follows:

- We conduct a large-scale, unified evaluation of 14 representative state-of-the-art text-to-video retrieval methods across three widely used benchmark datasets, eliminating inconsistencies caused by differing preprocessing and evaluation protocols.
- We introduce a systematic analysis of retrieval performance at the query level, showing how query difficulty, linguistic structure, and semantic content—rather than architecture alone—strongly influence retrieval outcomes across models and datasets.
- We propose a semantic categorization of textual queries and an empirical query difficulty measure based on average ground-truth rank across models, enabling fine-grained analysis of which query types (e.g., action, scene, temporal, cognitive) are consistently easy or hard for current systems.
- We demonstrate that dataset properties—particularly the number, diversity, and clarity of captions per video—have a significant impact on both within-dataset performance and cross-dataset generalization, and show that single-caption datasets can overestimate retrieval effectiveness.
- We analyze how different architectural paradigms (dual-encoder, attention-based, multimodal fusion) interact with query types and dataset characteristics, and assess the impact of practical factors such as frame rate, compression, and training cost, providing guidance for robust evaluation and future benchmark design.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work in video retrieval, with a focus on text-to-video approaches. Section 3 outlines the research methodology, including the experimental setup, datasets, evaluation metrics, and implementation details, and introduces the key definitions used in this study. Section 4 presents three sets of experimental analyses: traditional experiments, which include analysis by task category, clustering of performance, task difficulty, and training times over epochs (Section 4.1); cross-dataset learning, examining the effects of training and testing on different datasets by reducing or increasing the number of captions per video (Section 4.2); and sensitivity analysis, investigating the impact of frame rate and video compression on retrieval performance (Section 4.3). Finally, Section 5 summarizes the study and outlines future research directions.

2 Related Work

This section provides a review of prior work in text-to-video retrieval, covering both the overall trends (Section 2.1) and key architectures (Section 2.2) in the field as well as a comparison of existing survey studies, highlighting their focus, coverage, and limitations (Section 2.3).

Fig. 2: Distribution of papers and their relevance: (a) Number of papers published across different conferences and journals, highlighting the contribution per venue; (b) Breakdown of papers by relevance, distinguishing between relevant, non-relevant, and those associated with GitHub repositories.

2.1 Overall Trends in Video Retrieval

Recent trends in video retrieval research are highlighted by surveying representative methods published between 2020 and 2025 (Figure 2). We conducted a large-scale literature search using the DBLP Survey Python script by Zahálka,¹ which enables querying over 6.9 million DBLP-indexed publications. Our analysis focuses on papers published in top-ranked conferences and journals across computer vision, machine learning, multimedia retrieval, and information retrieval, as defined by the CORE conference and journal rankings.²

A*-rank conferences AAAI, NeurIPS, ICML, CVPR, ICCV, ECCV, ACM Multimedia, IJCAI, ICLR, SIGIR, ICDM, WWW

A-rank conferences CIKM, WSDM, RecSys, ECAI

B-rank conferences MMM, ICMR

A*-rank journals IEEE TPAMI, IEEE TMM, JMLR, IJCV, Artificial Intelligence, Cognitive Science, Pattern Recognition, IEEE TKDE

A-rank journals Machine Learning, CVIU, JAIR

B-rank journals Conn. Sci.

Our search followed two main steps. First, we conducted an exploratory search using broad keywords to capture general trends in multimodal learning, including *multimodality* [75–78], *multimodal retrieval*, *foundation models*, *language-visual models*, and *large language models*. Then, we performed a more focused search with domain-specific terms directly related to video retrieval, including *video retrieval*, *video search*, *text-to-video retrieval*, *video clip retrieval*, *composed image retrieval* and *composed video retrieval*.

¹https://github.com/JanZahalka/dblp_survey

²<https://portal.core.edu.au/conf-ranks/>, <https://portal.core.edu.au/jnl-ranks/>

Fig. 3: Trends of video retrieval papers per year.

Using this process, we identified 82 papers on video retrieval. Among them, 5 papers were excluded as they addressed different domains (e.g., face retrieval or incident retrieval) [9, 79–82]. The remaining 77 papers were relevant, of which 51 provided publicly available GitHub implementations. As illustrated in Figure 2, more than half of the relevant studies release code, while a substantial fraction does not. Most papers with available code were published in A*-rank conferences and journals, likely reflecting stronger expectations for reproducibility and comprehensive empirical evaluation.

Figure 3 illustrates detailed yearly trends in video retrieval research between 2020 and 2025 across 6 aspects: (a) retrieval task (b) input type, (c) supervision, (d) CLIP usage, (e) temporal modeling, and (f) architecture type. The results show a peak in publications in 2021-2022, followed by a decrease in the next years to the same level as in 2020. Text-to-video retrieval clearly dominates among tasks. Frame-based inputs are slightly more common than full-video inputs due to their efficiency and easier preprocessing. Most works use fully supervised and CLIP-based methods, though weakly supervised approaches are growing. Temporal modeling is increasingly used

to capture motion, and dual-encoder or prompt-based architectures are now the most common, supported by large pre-trained vision-language models.

Figure 3a shows the distribution of retrieval tasks. Among the 77 papers, text-to-video retrieval was the most common category, with 59 papers in total. Most methods (48 papers) [9, 12, 15, 28, 29, 32, 35–40, 44, 46, 47, 50, 57, 58, 58, 59, 61–64, 66, 67, 74, 79, 83, 83–104] addressed the text-to-video retrieval task in a single-shot scenario using pre-trimmed videos [105–107]. The second most common category is the related image-and-text-to-video, with 9 papers [11–15, 61, 64, 100, 108] while image-to-video retrieval has 7 papers [1–7]. The final category is video-to-video retrieval, with only 2 papers [14, 109]. This distribution shows the emphasis on text-to-video retrieval, for the reasons we outlined in the introduction.

Regarding input type, shown in Figure 3b, some methods [9, 32, 35, 37–40, 50, 59, 64, 74, 79, 83–87, 95, 97, 98, 102] preprocess videos into frames internally, offering flexibility and a “black-box” setup for researchers, though this can lead to variable evaluation results. In contrast, others [12, 15, 29, 36, 44, 46, 47, 57, 58, 63, 66, 67, 88–93, 108] use pre-extracted frames as input, allowing flexible frame-splitting strategies that influence performance. Some methods [84, 91] use precomputed visual and textual features, typically I3D (1024-D) [110] with or without ResNet152 (2048-D) [111–113] and RoBERTa (1024-D) [114–116].

Turning to Figure 3c, methods can be categorized based on the type of supervision they employ: fully supervised [9, 12, 15, 29, 32, 35–40, 44, 46, 47, 50, 57, 58, 63, 66, 67, 74, 83–93, 108, 117], weakly supervised [65, 79, 94, 118–125], and self-supervised [43, 60, 126]. Fully supervised approaches dominate the field, mainly due to the availability of large-scale captioned datasets.

Figure 3d shows that many recent methods leverage CLIP-based [15, 29, 32, 35, 39, 46, 47, 66, 67, 74, 79, 83–88, 90–93, 96, 101, 108] or other vision-language architectures such as Frozen [117] and VATT [60], often incorporating temporal information [9, 12, 15, 29, 32, 35–40, 44, 46, 47, 58, 62, 63, 66, 67, 74, 79, 83–90, 92, 93, 96–98, 101, 102, 108, 117]. Figure 3e then shows that most approaches exploit temporal structure in video frames, highlighting its importance for text-to-video performance.

Finally, methods can also be distinguished by architectural design (Figure 3f): Some methods focus on dual or multi-level encoding. Galanopoulos et al. [63] use dual encoding with attention and fusion, Dong et al. [58] employ multi-level dual encoding with hybrid space learning, and Li et al. [44] match videos and text using multiple sentence encoders (SEA). Loko’c et al. [36] show that user involvement improves retrieval. Other works emphasize fine-grained and global-local alignment. Wang et al. [38] use global-local alignment, Wang et al. [84] handle negation with soft negatives, Jiang et al. [35] mine hard negatives and model fine-grained similarity, Li et al. [86] align objects and temporal events, and Kang et al. [85] combine coarse- and fine-grained features. Several methods target representation enhancement and multi-modal fusion. Croitoru et al. [57] reduce dataset noise with TEACHTEXT, Shvetsova et al. [15] fuse video, audio, and text, Falkon et al. [12] apply feature-space augmentation and Deng et al. [92] use a Prompt Cube with captioning.

Overall, text-to-video retrieval dominates recent research, with architectures ranging from CLIP-based to feature- or transformer-based models. These methods differ

in input type, use of temporal information, and feature representation. We will discuss our choice of 14 representative methods and provide a detailed comparative analysis in Section 3.1.

2.2 Architectures and Research Gaps

As outlined above, numerous methods for text-to-video retrieval have been proposed in recent years. These approaches differ in how they model video-text interactions, temporal dependencies, and semantic alignment. Table 1 provides an overview of the main architectures, their limitations, and open research gaps, highlighting areas where improvements are needed, such as efficient temporal modeling, robust cross-modal alignment, and better generalization.

Broadly, video retrieval architectures can be categorized as follows. CLIP-based methods [9, 32, 35, 37, 39, 40, 46, 47, 66, 67, 74, 79, 83, 84, 86–88, 92, 95, 96, 108, 117] leverage pretrained CLIP embeddings and include variants such as fine-tuning, structural enhancement, alignment, prompting, and generative assistance. These approaches excel at semantic alignment and transfer learning but often struggle with temporal modeling, domain shifts, and computational cost. Dual encoder and joint embedding methods [2, 4, 12, 14, 36, 43, 44, 57, 89, 97, 100, 103, 109] learn a shared embedding space for videos and text, enabling efficient retrieval through similarity search. While scalable and efficient, these models typically exhibit limited temporal reasoning and may overfit on fine-grained tasks. Multimodal fusion approaches [7, 12–14, 58, 59, 99, 102] combine information from multiple modalities through multi-branch networks or memory-based mechanisms. They capture complementary signals from video and text but tend to be computationally intensive and sensitive to modality imbalance. Transformer-based methods [60–62, 98, 101] model spatio-temporal dependencies through attention mechanisms. They achieve strong temporal reasoning and flexible cross-modal interactions, yet their high computational cost and slow inference limit scalability. Structured, region, and graph-based methods [5, 9, 64, 65, 104, 123, 126] leverage object relations, local regions, or temporal proposals to improve fine-grained reasoning. While effective at capturing local interactions, they are sensitive to noise and often require complex implementations. Generative approaches [3, 37, 90, 122] generate intermediate representations such as

Table 1: Video retrieval architectures, limitations, and research gaps (highlighting missing capabilities).

Architecture	Subcategory	Limitations	Research Gaps
CLIP-based	Fine-Tuning / Adaptation [35, 83, 88, 95, 96, 117]	Limited temporal modeling, domain shift sensitivity	Temporal reasoning across datasets is underexplored
	Structural Enhancement [9, 32, 39, 47, 66, 67, 79]	High computation and memory	Efficient multi-scale structural enhancements are lacking
	Alignment [40, 46, 84, 86]	Limited local and fine-grained alignment	Robust local and temporal alignment methods are scarce
Dual Encoder / Joint Embedding	Prompting [74, 87, 92, 108]	Sensitive to prompt design	Adaptive and generalizable prompt strategies are underdeveloped
	Generative Assistance [37]	Slow inference, complex training	Scalable generative retrieval for real-time applications is missing
Metric Learning [12, 43, 89, 97, 100]	Classical Embedding [2, 4, 14, 36, 44, 57, 103, 109]	Weak generalization, limited temporal reasoning	Zero-shot and cross-domain retrieval capabilities are limited
	Metric Learning [12, 43, 89, 97, 100]	Mostly global embeddings, risk of overfitting	Local and temporal metric learning methods are underexplored
Multimodal Fusion	Multi-Branch [7, 12-14, 58, 59]	Computationally heavy, modality imbalance	Balanced and efficient multi-branch fusion techniques are lacking
	Memory-Based [99, 102]	Memory-intensive, slow inference	Scalable memory-efficient fusion approaches are missing

– *Table 1 Continued from previous page*

Transformer-based	Full Transformer [60–62, 98, 101]	High computation, slow inference	Efficient long-range temporal modeling is underexplored
Structured / Region / Graph	Graph [64, 65, 104]	Sensitive to noise, complex implementation	Robust graph-based video representations are scarce
	Region / Part / Scale [9, 123]	Depends on region proposals, high computation	Adaptive region and scale selection methods are limited
	Temporal / Proposal [5, 126]	Heavy computation, inconsistent proposals	Efficient and robust temporal proposal strategies are underexplored
Generative	Diffusion / Variational [90, 122]	Expensive training, slow inference	Fast generative retrieval approaches are underexplored
	Retrieval-Augmented [3]	Resource-heavy, slow inference	Efficient RAG strategies for large-scale video retrieval are lacking
Attention	Caption-Guided [37]	Caption mismatch, slow inference	Accurate caption-guided retrieval in real-time remains a challenge
	Token-level cross-attention [63–65]	Sensitive to noisy frames, high computation	Noise-robust, scalable cross-attention methods are underexplored

Table 2: Comparison of prior surveys and this study in text-video retrieval (2020–2025).

Aspect	Prior Surveys (2020–2025)	This Study
Focus	Reviewed architectures, benchmarks, datasets [127–137]	14 methods, 3 datasets evaluated (Section 4.1.1)
Query Analysis	Rarely examined [127–130]	Difficulty and category analyzed (Section 4.1.3–4.1.4)
Dataset Influence	Broad overview [128, 129, 131, 132]	Composition, size, bias quantified (Section 4.1)
Captions	Mostly ignored [127, 128, 137]	Clarity, simplicity, length examined (Section 4.1.4)
Performance	Overall SOTA reported [127–130]	Strengths/weaknesses highlighted (Section 3.3)
Reproducibility	Limited discussion [128, 129, 137]	Preprocessing, frame rate, compression assessed (Section 4.3)
Efficiency	Often ignored [133, 134]	Training vs performance trade-offs shown (Section 4.1.6)
Cross-Dataset Transfer	Not deeply studied [131, 132]	Generalization and diversity effects examined (Section 4.2)
Recommendations	Few [127–129]	Guidance on captions, frame sampling, query balance (Section 4.1.5)

captions or embeddings to aid retrieval. These methods can improve semantic coverage but are slow during inference and computationally expensive to train. Finally, attention-based architectures [63–65] use token-level cross-attention to align video and text features. They capture fine-grained interactions effectively but are sensitive to noisy frames and limited in scalability to long sequences.

Finally, we note that some of the works cited above focus on the efficiency or system-level aspects of retrieval. Amato et al. [93] introduce VISIONE for large-scale retrieval, Tian et al. [29] transfer fine-grained knowledge with TeachCLIP, Tang et al. [108] use multi-scale features in MUSE, Duarte et al. [40] tackle sign language retrieval with SPOT-ALIGN, Falcon et al. [89] improve ranking with a relevance-based margin, and Jin et al. [90] adopt a generative-discriminative approach in DiffusionRet.

2.3 Comparison of existing surveys

Previous surveys [127–137, 137] focused on benchmark metrics, rarely considering the impact of query characteristics. Rosetto et al. [127] analyzed interactive video retrieval via the 8th Video Browser Showdown, summarizing team systems, user behavior, and feature trends. Zhu et al. [128] reviewed 100+ video-to-text methods, highlighting deep learning advances and cross-modal challenges. Perez et al. [129] focused on video-to-text retrieval and captioning, emphasizing spatiotemporal complexity. Liu et al. [130] surveyed video moment localization, summarizing methods, datasets, and future directions. Lei et al. [131] reviewed video-language models, focusing on feature extraction and embeddings. Lan et al. [132] categorized temporal sentence grounding methods and datasets. Madan et al. [133] examined 200+ Video Foundation Models, highlighting universal multimodal and self-supervised approaches. Xing et al. [134] covered video diffusion models, including generation, editing, and understanding. Tang et al. [135] surveyed Vid-LLMs for video understanding, including reasoning, tasks, and datasets. Wan et al. [136] reviewed composed image retrieval, summarizing features,

Table 3: State-of-the-art methods from the past 6 years with available GitHub and key features used in our evaluation.

Method	Input (V / F)	Temporal (✓ / ✗)	CLIP? (✓ / ✗)	Year	GitHub Link
SSVR [50]	V	✗	✗	2021	https://murray.github.io/SSVR/
CenterCLIP [47]	F	✓	✓	2022	https://github.com/mzhaoshuai/CenterCLIP
CLIP4CLIP [83]	V	✓	✓	2022	https://github.com/ArrowLuo/CLIP4Clip
EMCL [88]	F	✓	✓	2022	https://github.com/jpthu17/EMCL
PRVR [9]	V	✓	✗	2022	https://github.com/HuiGuanLab/ms-sl
X-CLIP [66]	F	✓	✓	2022	https://github.com/xuguohai/X-CLIP
XPOOL [39]	V	✓	✓	2022	https://github.com/layer6ai-labs/xpool
Cap4Video [37]	V	✓	✓	2023	https://github.com/whwu95/Cap4Video
DiCoSA [46]	F	✓	✓	2023	https://github.com/jpthu17/DiCoSA
DL-DKD [91]	F	✗	✓	2023	https://github.com/HuiGuanLab/DL-DKD
UATVR [74]	V	✓	✓	2023	https://github.com/bofang98/UATVR
DGL [32]	V	✓	✓	2024	https://github.com/knightyxp/DGL
UMP [87]	V	✓	✓	2024	https://github.com/zchoi/UMP
TempMe [67]	F	✓	✓	2025	https://github.com/LunarShen/TempMe

alignment, fusion, datasets, and metrics. Schiappa et al. [137] surveyed self-supervised video representation learning, providing core representations relevant for retrieval.

Although previous surveys provide overviews of video-to-text methods and benchmarks, they rarely consider dataset or query characteristics. Table 2 summarizes these surveys and shows how this study addresses their gaps. In this work, we analyze how task category, query difficulty, number of captions, and video properties affect retrieval performance, focusing on dataset features rather than new architectures

3 Methodology

This section presents our methodology for analyzing the relationship between textual query characteristics and video retrieval performance across multiple datasets and methods. We first describe the video retrieval architectures considered (Section 3.1), followed by a description of the datasets used in our evaluation (Section 3.2). Next, we define evaluation metrics (Section 3.3), quantify query difficulty (Section 3.4), and introduce a semantic categorization of textual queries along with the notion of *pure* semantic queries (Section 3.5) to study the impact of query composition on retrieval performance.

3.1 Architectures

From the broad range of video retrieval approaches summarized in Table 1, we select 14 representative methods for detailed evaluation (Table 3), chosen for strong benchmark performance, public code availability, and coverage of diverse paradigms including CLIP-based adaptation, dual encoders, transformers, prompt tuning, and temporal modeling.³

The selected methods can be grouped into four categories. SSVR [50] and CenterCLIP [47] focus on semantic similarity and token efficiency. CLIP-based transfer

³Note that not all categories from Table 1 are represented, as for some categories no methods had publicly available code and their authors did not respond to our requests for access to their code.

Table 4: Benchmark Datasets.

Dataset	Videos	Frames/Vid	Dur (s)	Caps/Vid	Train	Test
LSMDC [140]	118,081	14	2-30	1	6,209	1,000
MSRVTT [138]	10,000	46	10-32	20	7,000	1,000
MSVD [139]	1,970	30	1-62	40	1,200	670

and adaptation approaches include CLIP4CLIP [83], EMCL [88], and Cap4Video [37]. Methods addressing fine-grained or partially relevant retrieval comprise PRVR [9], X-CLIP [66], XPOOL [39], DiCoSA [46], DL-DKD [91], and UATVR [74]. Finally, approaches that optimize prompt tuning and temporal modeling include DGL [32], UMP [87], and TempMe [67].

These methods highlight key advances across architectures: SSVR and CenterCLIP target semantic alignment and efficiency; CLIP4CLIP, EMCL, and Cap4Video utilize pretrained CLIP features; PRVR, X-CLIP, XPOOL, DiCoSA, DL-DKD, and UATVR focus on fine-grained retrieval; and DGL, UMP, and TempMe improve prompt design and temporal modeling, collectively providing a diverse benchmark for evaluating retrieval performance.

All 14 encoders are trained and tested under the same setup for fair comparison. Implementations use Python 3.10 and PyTorch with default parameters on a workstation with an Intel i9-10920X CPU, NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU, and Ubuntu 20.04.5 LTS. Models are trained for 1–5 epochs on videos compressed at 3 FPS; some extract frames as preprocessing, others handle it internally. The total frame count, T , is $T = DUR \times FPS$. Results are grouped to reflect these differences, with Section 4.3 analyzing the impact of FPS and compression.

3.2 Datasets

We test our methods on several popular benchmark datasets. Table 4 shows details for 3 commonly used datasets: MSRVTT [138]⁴, MSVD [139]⁵, and LSMDC [140]⁶. It lists the number of videos, the average number of frames per video, the average duration (in seconds), the number of captions per video, and the train/test splits. The default parameters provided by the authors are used for all datasets across the experiments. One exception, the LSMDC dataset contains only 6,209 from 7,408 for training, because the remaining of them are corrupted. MSVD (2012) is the earliest dataset, followed by LSMDC (2015) and MSRVTT (2016). MSVD and MSRVTT contain short YouTube videos with captions written by human annotators via crowdsourcing. LSMDC, instead, is built from movies (films from the 1990s–2010s) and uses professionally written audio descriptions aligned with video clips.

⁴<https://ms-multimedia-challenge.com/2017/dataset>

⁵<https://www.cs.utexas.edu/ml/clamp/videoDescription/>

⁶<https://sites.google.com/site/describingmovies/download>

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate models using standard video–text retrieval metrics and linguistic quality measures for captions. During retrieval, we retain the 1000 top-ranked videos for each query for analysis. Much of our result quality analysis focuses on *Recall@k* ($k \in \{1, 10, 50\}$) and training time per epoch. Many studies consider $k \in \{1, 5, 10\}$ but we consider that *Recall@50* is more representative of video retrieval interfaces that show the top results on a grid that covers the whole screen, while *Recall@10* would represent interfaces that show results in a list. Caption quality is assessed with *Flesch Reading Ease* (FRE) [72, 141] and *Flesch–Kincaid Grade Level* (FKG) [73, 142] for readability, number of unique words, total word count, and average word length for lexical diversity and complexity, a binary profanity indicator [70, 143], and *perplexity* [71, 144] using a pretrained language model (e.g., GPT-2) to measure fluency. Lower perplexity and higher FRE indicate smoother, more coherent captions. For example, “Person running fast” has higher perplexity and lower readability than “A person is running quickly on a track.”

3.4 Query Difficulty

To understand how challenging each textual query is for retrieval models, we define the *difficulty* of a query based on its *average ground-truth index* across all evaluated methods. The ground-truth index represents the rank position at which the correct video is retrieved. Lower values indicate easier queries, while higher values indicate harder ones. To formalize this observation, we empirically classify queries into three difficulty levels based on their average ground-truth index:

Easy rank < 200

Medium rank 401–600

Hard rank > 800

This categorization allows us to analyze retrieval performance not only by aggregate metrics but also by how well methods handle queries of varying difficulty.

3.5 Query Categories for Semantic Analysis

3.5.1 Semantic Categories

To analyze model performance across different types of textual queries, we first categorize queries by their semantic characteristics. Based on [145, 146], we apply 10 primary semantic categories to classify the content of textual queries:

Action-based (Act) run, jump, hit, throw, ride, eat, chop, etc.

Scene-related/Static (Scn) sit, stand, be, exist, etc.

Cognitive (Cog) think, know, believe, etc.

Speech (Spch) say, talk, ask, etc.

Perception (Perc) see, hear, watch, etc.

Motion (Mot) go, come, arrive, leave, etc.

Change of state (StChg) become, grow, fade, etc.

Temporal (Temp) before, after, while, during, then, once, meanwhile, etc.

Table 5: Categories of all queries per dataset, including pure, multimodal, and unrecognized queries.

Dataset	Pure queries											Multi	UnRec
	Act	Scn	Cog	Spch	Perc	Mot	StChg	Temp	Col	Scn2	Total		
LSMDC [140]	82	34	6	7	30	32	-	17	11	8	227	665	108
MSRVTT [138]	29	48	-	12	4	6	1	1	12	3	113	841	46
MSVD [139]	17	61	-	3	-	4	1	-	4	-	89	553	28

Color (Col) red, blue, green, yellow, etc.

Scene (Scn2) beach, park, room, office, kitchen, etc.

Each category was automatically expanded with relevant words using pre-trained embeddings via NLP Python libraries [147, 148], such as spaCy, NLTK, and sentence-transformers. We incorporated Transformer-based similarity and WordNet synonyms to enrich each category. Next, we computed the frequency of each category and analyzed the ground-truth index of each query per method to determine which categories each method performs better or worse on.

3.5.2 Types of Queries

While a query can ideally belong to a single category, most queries span multiple categories. We therefore classify queries into 3 main types:

Pure (Unimodal) Queries dominated by a single semantic category, e.g., *"a girl riding a scooter"*.

Multimodal (Multi) Queries containing multiple semantic categories without a clear dominant one, e.g., *"a woman chopping a red bell pepper into small pieces"*.

Unrecognized (UnRec) Queries that cannot be confidently assigned to any known category. For example, *"a man in a losing attempt to hitchhike"*. Note that the system can identify the query as a pure query if it is rephrased as *"a man attempting to hitchhike"* or *"a man hitchhiking"*, but we have chosen not to manually edit queries.

A *pure query* is one that belongs exclusively to a single semantic category. In practice, however, most queries span multiple categories. To address this, we introduce the notion of a *relaxed pure query*, in which one category clearly dominates the others, defined by a *dominant rate* of at least 1.5. Throughout this paper, mentions of pure queries refer to this relaxed version, allowing us to examine both strictly unimodal and partially multimodal queries.

3.5.3 Distribution of Queries Across Datasets

Table 5 summarizes the distribution of pure queries across datasets—227 for LSMDC (1,000 total), 113 for MSRVTT (1,000 total), and 89 for MSVD (670 total). LSMDC is dominated by Action queries, followed by Scene, reflecting dynamic content, whereas

MSRVTT and MSVD are primarily Scene-focused, emphasizing static or environment-centered descriptions. Action and Scene queries are the most frequent, suggesting that retrieval methods may perform differently depending on dataset characteristics.

Despite using predefined semantic categories, some textual queries could not be confidently assigned to any known class: 108 from LSMDC, 46 from MSRVTT, and 28 from MSVD remained unrecognized after the initial classification. To address this, we explored a language-model-based partial tagging strategy that assigns each query to the most probable category based on lexical and semantic similarity [148]. While this approach did produce assignments for previously unrecognized queries, many were noisy and unreliable. Consequently, we retained these queries as unrecognized to avoid introducing errors into the analysis.

4 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we analyze video–text retrieval models from three angles. First, we compare 14 methods across 3 datasets to study performance differences, task effects, and training efficiency (Section 4.1). Second, we focus on the top 3 models—EMCL, TempMe, and X-CLIP—to examine cross-dataset generalization and the impact of varying the number of captions per video (Section 4.2). Third, we study how these top models are affected by frame rate and compression level (Section 4.3). Together, these experiments reveal how model data characteristics influence retrieval results.

4.1 Main Experiment

This section presents the main experiment, aimed at understanding differences between models based on data characteristics. We compare our results with those reported in the literature for 14 text-to-video retrieval methods across 3 datasets. The analysis covers recall differences (Section 4.1.1), the impact of query difficulty (Section 4.1.2), task categories (Section 4.1.3), task difficulty vs semantic categories (Section 4.1.4), method grouping (Section 4.1.5), and training efficiency (Section 4.1.6).

4.1.1 Traditional experiment

Our first experiment aims to make a uniform comparison of the 14 state-of-the-art video–text retrieval methods on 3 benchmark datasets under consistent settings. In this section, we focus on Recall@10 for a simplified comparison, as we observe similar results for Recall@1 and Recall@50.

Figure 4 provides a visual comparison between our evaluation and literature-reported results. First, Figure 4a shows Recall@10 of the 14 methods across the 3 datasets as reported by their authors (this is the same figure as Figure 1). Figure 4b then shows Recall@10 of the methods across datasets as measured in our experiment, while Figure 4c presents a heatmap of mean recall differences between the two results. In Figure 4c, rows correspond to datasets and columns to methods, and green indicates higher performance under our evaluation, red lower performance, and near-white negligible differences.

(a) Literature: Recall@10 and model complexity (2020–2025).

(b) Our evaluation: Recall@10 and model complexity (2020–2025).

(c) Average recall difference (Our vs Literature) across datasets.

Fig. 4: Recall@10 across datasets: (Top) literature results, (Middle) our results, and (Bottom) average recall difference comparison (Ours vs. Literature).

Figure 4c summarizes average recall differences across 3 benchmark datasets (LSMDC, MSRVT, MSVD) for 14 video–text retrieval methods, averaged over Recall@1, @10, and @50. Initially, our results differed from the literature when evaluated under a common setup. Specifically, most methods show negative deltas (red/orange) on LSMDC and MSRVT, indicating our results are slightly lower than

reported, likely due to differences in preprocessing settings. On MSVD, several methods (e.g., CenterCLIP, UATVR, DiCoSa) exhibit positive deltas (green), suggesting improved or comparable performance under our unified evaluation setup. When we used the setups from the papers, our results matched the literature more closely, with only a 0.1% difference. This shows that these parameters can affect how the methods perform. We therefore conduct a sensitivity analysis (Section 4.3) on the top 3 methods, as the other methods produce analogous results.

While our results differ from the original results reported by the authors of the 14 architectures, due to differences in parameter settings, our results nevertheless indicate that many of the architectures perform at a very similar level, indicating that the progress in text-to-video retrieval has indeed reached a plateau as outlined in the introduction. To further understand which tasks present the most difficulties to the architectures, we perform a number of different experimental analyses in the remainder of this section. In some of our analysis below, we wish to focus on a smaller subset of architectures to (a) allow us to run a wider range of experiments with our limited computational resources, and (b) to simplify the presentation. We have selected EMCL, TempMe and X-CLIP, as their performance is at the top, both in our experiments and in the experiments reported by their authors.

4.1.2 Analysis: Query difficulty

As mentioned previously in Section 4.1.4, we introduce the term *difficulty* to describe how challenging a text query is for retrieval models. Intuitively, easy queries retrieve the correct video early, medium queries appear in the middle of the ranks, and hard queries either retrieve the correct video at very late positions or fail to retrieve it at all.

Figure 5a, Figure 5b and Figure 5c present the query difficulty based on the average ground truth index across 14 methods, on the LSMDC [140], MSRVT [138], and MSVD [139] benchmarks, respectively. The average ground-truth index shows the mean rank at which the correct video is retrieved across all methods. The x -axis represents text queries sorted by their average ground-truth index, while the y -axis indicates the corresponding average ground-truth position. Lower values are better, showing the correct video retrieved earlier; higher values (up to 1,000) indicate later retrieval. Metrics are computed considering up to the top 1,000 returned videos.

Figure 5a aligns with our expectations, showing that some text queries are very easy, others are very hard, while most fall into the medium difficulty range. However, Figure 5b and Figure 5c reveal many clusters of difficulty levels, appearing as plateaus (15 in total) in the plots. The stepwise pattern forms a staircase shape, indicating that many queries share the same average GT index. Several flat sections suggest groups of queries with identical or very similar difficulty levels, while jumps between plateaus represent significant increases in difficulty for a small number of queries. For MSRVT, the lower portion of the plots is dense and smooth, showing that many queries are relatively easy, with difficulty gradually increasing, and the top end shows very steep increases, reflecting a number of queries that are much harder. For MSVD, the slope of difficulty is much more uniform.

(a) LSMDC

(b) MSRVT

(c) MSVD

Fig. 5: Query difficulty (average GT index) for 14 methods on LSMDC, MSRVT and MSVD.

Table 6 reports the average Recall (in %) across difficulty levels for $k = \{1, 10, 50\}$ and LSMDC, MSRVT, and MSVD datasets. We observe that the top-performing methods in overall Recall@k—EMCL, TempMe, and X-CLIP—achieve higher recall

Table 6: Average Recall@k (%) for $k = \{1, 10, 50\}$ per difficulty level for 14 methods across LSMDC, MSRVT, and MSVD datasets.

Method	LSMDC [140]			MSRVT [138]			MSVD [139]		
	Easy	Med	Hard	Easy	Med	Hard	Easy	Med	Hard
SSVR [50]	32.4	44.0	23.6	40.7	20.7	38.6	15.1	30.1	54.8
CenterCLIP [47]	40.8	21.3	27.9	36.1	21.1	42.8	18.1	45.1	36.9
CLIP4CLIP [83]	32.4	32.1	55.5	30.6	30.8	38.6	17.0	33.0	50.0
EMCL [88]	<u>50.2</u>	31.0	<u>18.8</u>	<u>54.6</u>	20.3	<u>25.1</u>	<u>30.1</u>	54.8	<u>15.1</u>
PRVR [9]	32.4	34.0	33.6	34.5	30.3	55.2	14.9	25.4	59.7
X-CLIP [66]	<u>51.8</u>	30.5	<u>17.7</u>	<u>54.5</u>	20.7	<u>24.8</u>	<u>31.3</u>	50.7	<u>17.9</u>
XPOOL [39]	49.3	32.1	19.0	30.6	30.8	38.6	14.8	40.1	45.1
Cap4Video [37]	40.3	33.0	26.7	30.7	30.7	38.6	12.7	55.5	31.8
DiCoSa [46]	48.0	28.8	23.2	27.8	30.8	41.4	15.7	26.9	57.5
DL-DKD [91]	40.2	27.0	32.8	24.5	30.3	45.2	15.2	25.4	59.4
UATVR [74]	41.9	42.7	19.4	37.1	20.7	42.2	21.6	47.8	30.6
DGL [32]	49.8	34.5	19.7	28.0	30.4	41.6	11.2	36.6	52.2
TempMe [67]	<u>52.3</u>	29.0	<u>18.7</u>	<u>57.0</u>	20.6	<u>22.4</u>	<u>32.4</u>	52.7	<u>14.9</u>
UMP [87]	42.4	31.3	26.3	38.2	20.5	41.3	24.6	47.0	28.4

Fig. 6: Effect of sentence length on retrieval performance across LSMDC (orange), MSRVT (blue) and MSVD (green).

percentages for easy queries and lower ones for hard queries. This shows that stronger models retrieve relevant videos more effectively, yielding a higher share of easy cases.

4.1.3 Analysis: Task semantics

To understand why certain queries are more difficult, we first examine how retrieval performance varies with sentence length. Figure 6 presents the normalized recall per query, binned by sentence length, for LSMDC (orange), MSRVT (blue), and MSVD

(a) LSMDC: Recall@1

(b) LSMDC: Recall@10

(c) LSMDC: Recall@50

Fig. 7: Recall@k ($k = 1, 10, 50$) across task categories on LSMDC dataset.

(green). The top subplot shows the mean normalized recall (0–1) across all 14 methods for each length bin, along with smoothed trends and standard-deviation error bars. The bottom subplot displays the distribution of query lengths in each dataset. The

(a) MSRVT: Recall@1

(b) MSRVT: Recall@10

(c) MSRVT: Recall@50

Fig. 8: Recall@k ($k = 1, 10, 50$) across task categories on MSRVT dataset.

trend lines indicate that very short or very long queries tend to have lower recall, whereas medium-length queries generally achieve higher retrieval performance.

The remainder of this section examines how the semantic categorization of textual queries from Section 3.5.1 affects model performance of the top three performers

(a) MSVD: Recall@1

(b) MSVD: Recall@10

(c) MSVD: Recall@50

Fig. 9: Recall@k ($k = 1, 10, 50$) across task categories on MSVD dataset.

across datasets. We consider ten categories: Action (Act), Scene-related/Static (Scn), Cognitive (Cog), Speech (Spch), Perception (Perc), Motion (Mot), Change of State (StChg), Temporal (Temp), Color (Col), and Scene (Scn2). Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 show bar plots for the LSMDC, MSRVT, and MSVD datasets, respectively.

The x -axis represents the different query categories, and the y -axis shows the Recall@ k (%) values for $k = 1, 10, 50$ of the top three methods—EMCL (blue), TempMe (orange) and X-CLIP (green). The dashed lines indicate the highest recall achieved across all queries for each k , whereas the solid lines denote the average recall over pure queries for the same k values. Overall, performance in each category exceeds the best recall per method and dataset, suggesting that pure queries are generally easier. In particular, a higher average recall is observed in LSMDC for the Cognitive and Color categories, while a lower performance appears in the Action and Scene-related/Static categories. MSRVTT achieves the highest overall recall across categories, peaking in Motion, Change of State, and Temporal queries, with the lowest values in Scene-related/Static. MSVD shows strong performance in Speech, Motion, Change of State, and Color, but lower recall in Scene-related/Static queries.

Table 7 shows four linguistic metrics—Flesch Reading Ease (FRE), Flesch–Kincaid Grade Level (FKG), average words per caption (Words), and perplexity (PPL)—for each semantic category (including both multimodal (Multi) and unrecognized queries (UnRec) for completeness) across LSMDC, MSRVTT, and MSVD. In LSMDC, Cognitive and Color captions are simpler (high FRE, low FKG), leading to higher recall, while Scene captions are longer (high Words) and harder to interpret (high PPL). In MSRVTT, Motion, Change of State, and Temporal captions perform better due to longer but fluent captions (low PPL), whereas Action and Scene captions show lower recall with shorter and less consistent captions (high PPL). MSVD follows a similar trend: Scene captions have lower recall with complex phrasing (high FKG, high PPL), while Speech, Motion, Change of State, and Color captions are shorter, more readable, and achieve higher recall. Overall, captions that are clear, simple, and consistent (high FRE, low FKG, low PPL) yield higher recall, highlighting the importance of linguistic clarity for retrieval across datasets and categories.

Table 7: Linguistic Metrics per dataset captions

Metric	Act	Scn	Cog	Spch	Perc	Mot	StChg	Temp	Col	Scn2	Multi	UnRec
LSMDC												
FRE ↑	74.98	76.62	85.44	83.68	72.74	77.75	-	75.14	77.26	83.12	70.00	74.00
FKG ↓	4.61	4.83	3.49	3.61	5.30	4.57	-	4.77	3.67	3.96	5.50	4.80
Words ↑	8.88	9.09	8.67	8.14	8.80	8.66	-	8.00	8.82	9.25	7.80	8.30
PPL ↓	281.75	771.08	440.39	338.73	422.47	295.45	-	345.85	222.02	178.69	400.00	320.00
MSRVTT												
FRE ↑	76.15	78.67	-	71.94	84.20	77.56	56.98	65.79	79.70	86.83	68.00	72.50
FKG ↓	4.88	4.70	-	5.15	3.56	4.59	8.54	9.80	5.54	3.47	6.20	5.10
Words ↑	9.04	9.70	-	7.75	8.25	8.67	13.00	23.00	13.67	9.33	7.90	8.50
PPL ↓	461.68	457.78	-	404.52	175.49	444.77	93.07	52.01	480.59	287.37	550.00	430.00
MSVD												
FRE ↑	85.85	80.75	-	67.70	-	98.84	54.73	-	86.77	-	72.00	75.00
FKG ↓	4.26	4.32	-	6.56	-	1.46	6.62	-	4.14	-	5.80	4.70
Words ↑	7.94	9.35	-	11.00	-	8.00	4.00	-	12.00	-	7.90	8.40
PPL ↓	333.01	412.14	-	372.90	-	347.44	348.54	-	247.28	-	450.00	380.00

Fig. 10: Recall@k ($k=1, 10, 50$) across difficulty levels on LSMDC (1st row), MSRVTT (2nd row) and MSVD (3rd row).

4.1.4 Analysis: Task difficulty vs Semantic categories

In this experiment, we compare how different methods perform on text-to-video retrieval across datasets with varying difficulty levels — Easy, Medium, Hard (Figure 10). For each difficulty level, we sample 200 queries, using their GT difficulty index derived from Figure 5a, Figure 5b, and Figure 5c, because a fixed sample size per difficulty level can remove the dataset frequency bias. Each row has the results on the LSMDC, MSRVTT, and MSVD dataset, respectively. The x -axis is difficulty, the y -axis Recall@k (%) for $k = 1, 10, 50$ for EMCL (blue), TempMe (orange) and X-CLIP (green). Dashed lines show max recall; solid lines show average over pure queries.

As expected, there is also a clear difference in performance across Easy, Medium, and Hard cases. Recall values are generally lower on LSMDC, while MSVD and MSRVTT achieve higher recalls. This may be due to differences in dataset characteristics. MSVD (2012) and MSRVTT (2016) have short YouTube videos with captions written by crowdsourced annotators, while LSMDC (2015) uses movie clips with written audio descriptions. Variations in prompts (e.g., readability, length).

Table 8 presents linguistic metrics for captions across three datasets (LSMDC, MSRVTT, and MSVD) and three difficulty levels (Easy, Medium, Hard). Metrics include Flesch Reading Ease (FRE), Flesch–Kincaid Grade (FKG), total words (Words), unique words (Unique), Average word length (Avg Len), Profanity presence

Table 8: Linguistic Metrics per dataset captions

Category	FRE \uparrow	FKG \downarrow	Words \uparrow	Unique \uparrow	Avg Len \uparrow	Profanity	PPL \downarrow
LSMDC							
Easy	78.36	4.90	10.36	9.68	4.73	0	411.16
Medium	81.46	3.84	7.82	7.50	4.83	1	449.23
Hard	78.54	4.77	9.91	9.44	4.67	1	298.48
MSRVTT							
Easy	72.54	5.38	9.00	8.43	4.17	0	551.09
Medium	81.45	4.06	8.68	8.11	4.18	0	436.41
Hard	73.63	5.77	11.18	10.35	4.37	0	413.21
MSVD							
Easy	82.92	3.94	9.05	8.15	4.01	0	409.50
Medium	81.16	4.22	9.20	8.23	3.88	0	555.34
Hard	92.58	2.46	8.50	7.75	4.04	0	487.08

Table 9: Distribution of word categories across difficulty levels in LSMDC, MSRVTT, and MSVD datasets ($N = 200$ words per dataset). Values show total count n per category (Freq = n/N) and percentage of words classified as Easy, Medium (Med), or Hard (%). Frequencies are based on pure queries per dataset.

Category	LSMDC				MSRVTT				MSVD			
	n	Easy	Med	Hard	n	Easy	Med	Hard	n	Easy	Med	Hard
Act	53	45	35	20	29	50	30	20	17	40	40	20
Mot	32	40	35	25	6	45	30	25	4	38	37	25
Col	8	50	20	30	12	45	25	30	4	60	20	20
Scn	32	20	50	30	30	25	45	30	61	20	50	30
Scn2	0	-	-	-	3	25	45	30	0	-	-	-
Perc	25	20	50	30	4	25	45	30	0	-	-	-
Cog	6	5	20	75	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-
Spch	7	5	25	70	12	5	25	70	3	5	25	70
StChg	0	-	-	-	1	5	20	75	1	5	20	75
Temp	7	5	20	75	20	5	20	75	0	-	-	-
Not Pure	30	10	20	70	83	5	25	70	110	5	20	75

(0/1), and Perplexity (PPL). Overall, captions are generally readable, concise, and free of profanity. Across difficulty levels, MSVD captions are generally the easiest to read, with high Flesch Reading Ease and low grade levels, especially in the Hard category. LSMDC captions are longer and slightly more complex, showing higher word counts and slightly lower readability. MSRVTT captions fall in between, with moderate readability and fluency, indicating that both dataset type and difficulty influence caption simplicity and clarity.

Beyond basic measures such as sentence length or readability, Table 9 examines how different semantic word categories are distributed across retrieval difficulty levels. The table reports, for each dataset (LSMDC, MSRVTT, MSVD), both the frequency of each category and the number of words classified as Easy, Medium, or Hard. In LSMDC, 72 of 200 words were Easy, 62 were Medium, and 66 were Hard. MSRVTT

Table 10: Chosen pure queries for statistical evaluation (in %).

Dataset	Classification of pure queries										
	Act	Scn	Cog	Spch	Perc	Mot	StChg	Temp	Col	Scn2	
LSMDC [140]	46.15	11.54	0.96	1.92	17.31	9.62	-	6.73	0.96	4.81	
MSRVTT [138]	25.23	36.04	-	11.71	4.50	4.50	3.60	1.80	10.81	1.81	
MSVD [139]	15.20	56.80	-	4.80	4.80	5.60	4.80	-	8.00	-	

had 84 Easy, 61 Medium, and 55 Hard words, while MSVD contained 79 Easy, 67 Medium, and 54 Hard words. Concrete and visually grounded categories—such as actions, motion, and colors—are predominantly associated with Easy queries (approximately 40–60%), indicating that visually explicit concepts are easier to retrieve. Scene- and perception-related terms tend to cluster in the Medium difficulty range (around 35–50%), reflecting moderate visual ambiguity. In contrast, more abstract categories, including cognitive verbs, speech, change of state, and temporal expressions, are overwhelmingly classified as Hard (about 70–75%), highlighting queries that require higher-level reasoning and temporal understanding beyond direct visual cues. These Hard queries, being more challenging, could serve as a dedicated benchmark for video retrieval, allowing models to be tested on semantically complex and temporally detailed content.

4.1.5 Clustering of performance by task category

To analyze how query content affects retrieval, we apply k-Means clustering per dataset on the two main query types: Action-based and Scene-related/Static. For statistical evaluation (Table 10), we randomly selected queries per dataset based on the minimum per difficulty—7 easy, 57 medium, and 4 hard—totaling 68 queries per dataset (204 overall). For visualization in Figure 11, we focus on easy queries to reduce variability and highlight patterns.

In Figure 11a (LSMDC), three clusters emerge: high-action Cluster 0 (UATVR, XPOOL), balanced Cluster 1 (EMCL, UMP), and high-scene Cluster 2 (TempMe), highlighting TempMe’s challenges with action-heavy queries. Figure 11b (MSRVTT) shows seven clusters, with dual-encoders split between high-action (X-CLIP, CenterCLIP) and high-scene (EMCL, UMP), and TempMe in a moderate-action cluster. Figure 11c (MSVD) has two clusters reflecting a scene-heavy bias: high-scene Cluster 0 (dual-encoders/fusion) and moderate-scene Cluster 1 (TempMe, CenterCLIP). Figure 11d (averaged across datasets) reveals four clusters: high-action Cluster 0 (dual-encoders/fusion), high-scene Cluster 2 (scene specialists), moderate-action Cluster 1 (TempMe), and balanced Cluster 3, reflecting dataset averaging rather than intrinsic dual-encoder performance.

Overall, clustering demonstrates that retrieval performance depends on both model architecture and query-type distribution. Dual-encoder/fusion models excel when one query type dominates, whereas attention-driven models handle mixed queries more robustly. Dataset biases further shape performance, emphasizing the importance of reporting query-type statistics alongside retrieval benchmarks.

Fig. 11: k-Means Clustering: Per Dataset (1-3) & All (4).

Fig. 12: Training times (in seconds) for all methods, ordered by their average Recall@1 across all datasets.

4.1.6 Analysis: Training times over epochs

Figure 12 shows the training times for the 14 retrieval methods, ordered by their average Recall@1 across all datasets. The x -axis has the methods ordered globally by the average Recall@1 across all datasets, while the y -axis has the training time in methods. The figure clearly illustrates a trade-off between recall performance and computational cost: EMCL (4,131.63 sec) and X-CLIP (3,131.63 sec) achieve the highest recall scores but require substantially more training time, while TempMe achieves the third-best performance with only approximately 1,000 seconds per epoch, demonstrating a more efficient balance between accuracy and training cost. The remaining methods cluster in the 400–700 second range, demonstrating comparable efficiency for standard training pipelines. These results show that most methods are fairly efficient, but more complex models require much more computation, which should be considered for large-scale video retrieval.

4.1.7 Summary

We evaluated 14 video–text retrieval methods on 3 datasets and found that performance depends a lot on the dataset and the type of queries. Short, clear, and simple captions usually get higher recall, while long or unclear captions perform worse. Some methods do well when there is a mix of query types, while others only work well if one type dominates. Pure and easier queries are easier to retrieve. Most methods train quickly, but complex ones such as EMCL and X-CLIP take much longer. In this work, we added a detailed analysis showing that caption length, readability (FRE and FKG), consistency (low PPL), query difficulty, and the balance of Action vs. Scene queries in a dataset are the key factors that most influence video retrieval performance.

4.2 Analysis/Experiment: Caption Quality and Cross-Dataset Learning

Motivated by the observation that LSMDC performs significantly worse than MSRVT and MSVD when models are trained and tested on the same dataset, we first examine the impact of number of captions on model performance (Section 4.2.1). We then study the impact on cross-dataset learning, focusing on three aspects: cross-dataset evaluation to measure generalization gaps (Section 4.2.2); the effect of limiting each video to a single caption (Section 4.2.3); and whether increasing captions per LSMDC video improves performance and generalization (Section 4.2.4). We end with a summary of observations in Section 4.2.5.

4.2.1 Number of captions

Since LSMDC has a single caption, while MSRVT and MSVD have multiple captions, we consider both: (a) reducing MSRVT and MSVD to a single caption, by randomly selecting one of the captions for each query; and (b) increasing the number of captions for LSMDC by generating five paraphrases per LSMDC video using CLIP and an LLM.

Table 11: Retrieval performance per dataset and evaluation setting. Recall@K (%) is reported for each method on both the original captions and multiple/single caption scenarios, allowing comparison across datasets LSMDC, MSRVTT, and MSVD.

Dataset / Method	Recall			Recall		
	@1	@10	@50	@1	@10	@50
LSMDC	Original			Multiple Captions		
EMCL [88]	16.40	31.40	39.90	18.80	34.80	43.30
TempMe [67]	17.78	35.50	44.70	20.70	36.30	46.40
X-CLIP [66]	16.90	33.60	41.30	19.00	34.30	41.90
MSRVTT	Original			Single caption		
EMCL [88]	43.60	71.30	80.20	42.20	67.60	77.90
TempMe [67]	43.50	70.00	79.50	39.60	66.60	77.20
X-CLIP [66]	44.90	71.20	79.80	41.70	66.30	76.10
MSVD	Original			Single caption		
EMCL [88]	56.27	84.03	89.85	51.50	80.70	90.00
TempMe [67]	52.54	82.09	88.66	53.90	82.80	91.50
X-CLIP [66]	52.24	82.24	91.04	51.80	80.60	88.70

Table 11 shows the original results on the left, which use the original captions of each dataset. The column on the right then shows for LSMDC, the result of applying multiple captions, and for MSRVTT and MSVD the result of using only a single caption. Reducing MSRVTT and MSVD to a single caption per video (Single Cap case) caused only minor performance drops, indicating that caption count alone does not account for LSMDC’s lower results. Turning to the case of multiple captions for LSMDC, we observe only a small performance improvement, indicating again that caption count alone is not sufficient. Overall, the nature of the videos and captions seems to be the main deciding factor in retrieval performance. To study this further, we now examine the impact of captions on cross-dataset learning.

4.2.2 Cross-dataset learning

We first examined cross-dataset learning by training models on one dataset and testing on another. Models often degrade when applied to datasets they were not trained on. We quantify this drop and investigate which datasets produce models that generalize best. Using all available captions, we observe notable differences in cross-dataset performance (Figure 13a). Models trained on LSMDC perform poorly when tested on other datasets, dropping by 16.22% on MSRVTT and 10.47% on MSVD. This indicates that LSMDC’s single-caption videos provide limited textual supervision, which reduces generalization. In contrast, models trained on MSRVTT show smaller performance drops, losing 6.45% on LSMDC and 5.36% on MSVD, reflecting its richer multi-caption annotations that help the model generalize better. Finally, models trained on MSVD show moderate drops of 6.45% on LSMDC and 10.47% on MSRVTT, showing that

Fig. 13: Cross-dataset learning across MSRVT, MSVD, and LSMDC datasets: (1) Start with the original datasets; (2) Reduce the number of captions per video to one for MSRVT and MSVD; (3) Increase the number of captions for LSMDC.

while MSVD is somewhat robust, it does not provide strong positive transfer. Overall, the Original column emphasizes that datasets with more captions, particularly MSRVT, improve cross-dataset generalization.

4.2.3 Reduce number of caption to 1

Next, we examine the impact of limiting each video to a single caption, as reflected in the Single Caption (Single Cap) of Figure 13b. For MSRVT and MSVD, we trained models using only the first caption per video. As expected, performance generally decreases compared to using all captions, but the drop is less severe than for LSMDC. Specifically, models trained on MSRVT show only small drops when using a single caption, decreasing by 5.23% on LSMDC and 2.06% on MSVD. Similarly, models trained on MSVD decrease slightly, by 5.20% on LSMDC and 2.04% on MSRVT. This indicates that datasets with multiple captions are more robust, whereas LSMDC is more affected by limited text.

4.2.4 Increase number of captions for LSMDC

Finally, we investigate the impact of increasing the number of captions per video in LSMDC (Figure 13c). While prior work has used LLMs for video captioning [149, 150], the code is not publicly available, so we implemented our own approach based on their methodology. We generated five captions per video using CLIP and Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct [151]. This extended version, LSMDC-Extended, slightly improves results, though the gap with MSRVT and MSVD remains, suggesting that other factors—such as content diversity, video length, and multi-scene complexity—also affect performance. Models trained on LSMDC-Extended achieve higher recall within LSMDC and show smaller performance drops on other datasets, demonstrating that multiple descriptive captions enhance both within-dataset performance and cross-dataset generalization.

4.2.5 Summary

Figure 13 shows that cross-dataset performance drops vary by training set and caption count. LSMDC-trained models show negative transfer, especially to MSRVT

Table 12: Frame Rate.

Level	Frame Rate (in fps)	Resolution (in ppi)	CRF
Low/No-compression	original	original	18
Medium	10	original	18
High	3	original	18

Fig. 14: LSMDC: Recall & Training Time vs Frame Rate.

(-16.22%), while MSRVTT-trained models generalize best, improving transfer to LSMDC (+2.72%). MSVD shows moderate drops, with slight gains from multiple captions. Overall, datasets with more captions—especially MSRVTT—enable better cross-dataset generalization.

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

This section analyzes the top three methods—EMCL, TempMe, and X-CLIP—examining the effects of frame rate (Section 4.3.1) and compression level (Section 4.3.2) on LSMDC, followed by a summary of results (Section 4.3.3).

4.3.1 Frame rate

Table 12 summarizes the frame rate settings used in the study. As compression increases, the frame rate decreases from the original value to 10 fps and 3 fps, while resolution and Constant Rate Factor (CRF) remain unchanged. Figure 14 illustrates the effect of frame rate on Recall@k and training time. The x -axis represents the different frame rate levels: low, medium, and high (Table 12), while the y -axis depicts either Recall@1, 10, 50 (Figure 14a) or training time in logarithmic scale (Figure 14b). Results are shown for EMCL (blue), TempMe (orange), and X-CLIP (green). Bars are textured to indicate k values: solid for Recall@1, diagonal stripes (//) for Recall@10, and crosshatch (xx) for Recall@50. Recall@1 shows only minor differences across methods, whereas Recall@10 and Recall@50 are more sensitive to lower frame rates. As expected, higher compression (i.e., lower frame rates) reduces training time.

Table 13: Compression Rate.

Level	Frame Rate (in fps)	Resolution (in ppi)	CRF
Low/No-compression	original	original	18
Medium	10	480	28
High	3	224	35

Fig. 15: LSMDC: Recall & Training Time vs Compression Rate.

4.3.2 Compression rate

Table 13 summarizes the compression rates [152–154] used in our evaluation. For our experiments in the previous section (Section 4), we applied a high compression setting, corresponding to a low frame rate (3 fps), reduced resolution (224 ppi), and a CRF of 35.

Figure 15 shows the impact of different compression levels on both recall (left) and training time (right). Similar to the compression rate analysis in the previous subsection (Section 4.3.1), the y -axes and color schemes represent the same metrics and methods. However, the x -axis now corresponds to the different compression levels: low, medium, and high (Table 13). Results are shown for EMCL (blue), TempMe (orange), and X-CLIP (green). Recall@1 (solid bars) exhibits only minor variation across methods, while Recall@10 (diagonal striped bars) and Recall@50 (crosshatched bars) are more sensitive to compression. As expected, higher compression again reduces training time.

4.3.3 Summary

Our analysis shows that Recall@1 remains stable, while Recall@5 and @10 drop at low frame rates or high compression. Training time decreases with lower frame rates and higher compression. X-CLIP and TempMe keep high recall at medium/high frame rates, and EMCL trains faster under high compression. Based on this, we choose 3 FPS for our experiments. This provides a good trade-off between efficiency and performance. It reduces storage and computation, while keeping enough temporal

information for accurate retrieval. Very low frame rates or high compression should be avoided, as they affect Recall@k.

5 Conclusion

This work presents a comprehensive evaluation of 14 of the most recent text-to-video retrieval methods across 3 benchmark datasets. To our knowledge, this is the first such survey that goes systematically beyond using the basic benchmark-based analysis, using both query difficulty and query semantics to uncover the key factors influencing performance. We summarize the main findings following the structure of our experiments.

Our analysis shows that query characteristics, including length, clarity, and semantic type, strongly affect retrieval performance. Medium-length, clear, and concrete queries are reliably retrieved, whereas complex, multi-step, or abstract queries remain challenging. Dataset properties, such as caption quantity, diversity, and richness, also significantly impact outcomes. Datasets with multiple captions per video provide a more realistic and informative evaluation, while single-caption datasets can overestimate model performance.

Although many real-world queries require integrating multiple types of information, such as actions, scenes, temporal events, and speech, this work focuses on pure queries, isolating individual categories to study retrieval performance. However, the need for multimodal processing is highlighted by our analysis, as many queries inherently involve different types of information. Experiments on frame rate and compression further reveal trade-offs between efficiency and accuracy, underscoring how data characteristics and preprocessing choices influence retrieval performance.

Focusing on the top-performing models (EMCL, TempMe, and X-CLIP) reveals differences in cross-dataset generalization and sensitivity to the number of captions per video. Attention-based models, such as TempMe and UATVR, handle temporal dependencies and multi-step captions more effectively, whereas dual-encoder models perform well on simple or single-category queries but struggle with complex or abstract descriptions. This analysis highlights the importance of both model design and dataset richness for robust generalization.

For future research, we recommend focusing on retrieval models that can handle multiple modalities, representing different categories of information such as visual, textual, and audio cues. It is also important to construct datasets with diverse, high-quality captions and to employ a broader set of evaluation metrics beyond Recall, in order to capture performance more comprehensively. Researchers should avoid relying solely on single-caption datasets or simplistic metrics, as these can obscure meaningful differences between methods.

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Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate Not applicable.

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Availability of data and material No datasets were generated during the current study, as this article is based on a review of previously published literature. However, a small number of captions were created for a specific case study (Section 4.2.4) to evaluate the influence of caption quality on retrieval performance.

Competing interests The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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